

Additional file 11. Primers used for qPCR analysis

Oligo name	Target gene ID	Name of gene	Length of oligos	Sequence (5'-3')	Efficiency
DFC2_1F DFC2_1R	CAA01634	AXE	194	CTGGACGATTAGCGAGTACG CGCAGGTGGAATTCCATCC	2.1
ACT11 for ACT11 rev	Potri.006G192700	ACTIN	208	TATTGTTCTCAGTGGTGGCTCT GGACTCATCATACTCTGCCTTT	1.9
CYP for CYP rev	Potri.004G168800	CYP	234	TAAGACCGAATGGCTTGACG AGAACGCACCCCAAACTACTA	2.0
TUB_for TUB_rev	Potri.001G464400	TUB	200	ATCCCTCGCCTTCATTTCT CCTCTTTCGTGCTCATCTTACC	1.9
UBQ-L_for UBQ-L_rev	Potri.005G198700	UBQ	200	TGGCAAGACCATAACTCTCG CTCCCCTAAGCCTCAAACC	1.9
COMT-F COMT-R	Potri.012G006400	COMT	125	AGCACAATCGTCTCCAAGTACCCT AACATTCTCCACACCAGGGAAAGC	2.0
F5H-F F5H-R	Potri.007G016400	F5H	125	AAGCCAATATAGGCAAGCCTGTGAATC ATTTTTAGCCCCGAAAGCTGCTCTG	1.9
GT43Afor1 GT43Arev1	Potri.006G131000	GT43A	213	GTCGCCCTTCATCTGTCC TCCCTCATAGTTTTCTCCTGCT	2.1
GT43Bfor1 GT43Brev1	Potri.016G086400	GT43B	183	GTCGCCCTTCTTCAGTCCAG TTTTGTCTTCTTGATTTTCCTGA	2.0